

PERSONNEL MANAGEMENT TECHNIQUES

Sufiyev Rustam

teacher of Ferghana State University.

Khamidov Elyorjon

teacher of Fergana State University.

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Abstract. Leadership should not be a means and method of coercion, but a means of coordinating the actions of members of the work team acting in common interests. This article analyzes the current personnel management processes and methods.

Key words: personnel, management, personnel management, management method, enterprise, leadership style, leadership function.

The concept of "leadership style" is used in leadership, as well as management styles related to the differentiation of the methods of influence of subjects on management objects. The leadership style is understood as the method of the leader's communication with the subordinates in the process of fulfilling his service obligations, it is expressed by the directive effect, the level of manifestation of the leader's sole will. In this approach, solving pressing problems relies on adherence to the principles of justice and respect for the rights of all parties involved in the case. People united by work should be close to each other.

The democratic style of management implies wide participation of personnel, employees in production and labor activities, that is, democratization of management. This method is expressed by collective leadership, the participation of experts in the development of management decisions, the awareness of employees about the decisions being prepared, and the consideration of their attitude. The main manifestations of the democratic leadership style are as follows:

- transfer of leadership functions, certain types of authority to subordinates, acceptance of certain decisions by subordinates;
- taking into account the advice and recommendations of subordinates and other authorized persons;
- the ability of the leader to agree with the points of view and opinions of other persons;
- trusting subordinates, tending to them, tending to communicate, maintaining moderation in communication with personnel;
- selection of qualified and literate specialists in terms of business qualities;
- the leader's self-criticism, self-improvement, and professional development;
- the reasonableness of disciplinary requirements, the compatibility of the organization's success with their interests.

A comparison of leadership styles, at first glance, indicates the undoubted superiority of democracy. But it would be a mistake to conclude about its absoluteness. Acceptability of one or another leadership style depends on the situation. In addition, there is a personal opinion of leaders, on the basis of which they follow the style according to their nature and views. In this case, the following types of leadership are shown:

- production is mainly directed towards achieving the goals of production activity;

- social, in which the leader takes special care of working conditions and payment, satisfaction of employees, prevention of social conflicts and conflicts in the team;
- production-social - combines the characteristics of the first and second types;
- contact, relies on the leader's personal contacts and direct communication with subordinates;
- characteristic of managers inclined to remote, office-based, direct communication with employees "at a distance";
- distanced, in which the leader tries to stay away from the direct performance of management functions, prefers that the processes take place by themselves.

Leaders who involve the company's personnel to participate in management processes and use their opportunities for the interests of the company rather than for their personal interests are called democratic leaders.

The leadership style chosen and used by the leader should correspond to the requirements of modern management and the nature of managers' behavior. According to Garry Yukla, a specialist in personnel leadership and management, it is necessary to embody the appropriate types of behavior of the leader that form a certain system. The system includes the following areas:

- 1) Focus on production.
- 2) Paying attention to subordinates.
- 3) Inspire the team, increase enthusiasm.
- 4) Involving personnel in the decision-making process.
- 5) Rewarding employees based on their contribution to the company's well-being.
- 6) Coordinating the actions of the executors during the execution of the work.
- 7) If necessary, involve consultants who can develop recommendations and give advice on improving the quality of work.
- 8) Maintaining labor discipline related to labor and production.

The theoretical importance of the classification of personnel management efficiency factors, it fully reveals to us the essence of labor productivity, determines the relationship between the factors. Taking into account the specific characteristics of each specific direction of the company's activity, the characteristics of the influence of factors are revealed.

Table 1

Classification of factors affecting the effectiveness of personnel management

Factors	Content of factors
Physiological factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Gender and age; • health; • mental and physical abilities, etc.
Technical and technological factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • nature of tasks to be solved; • complexity of work; • technical support; • use of scientific and technical achievements, etc.;

Structural and organizational factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • working conditions; • ratio of the number of personnel categories; • enterprise size; • work mode and length of service; • personnel qualification and level of its use, etc.
Socio-economic factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • material incentives; • social benefits; • standard of living, etc.
Socio-spiritual factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • moral atmosphere in the team; • psychophysiological condition of employees; • career prospects in the service, etc.
Regional and situational factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • location of the enterprise; • level of competition; • inflation and unemployment; • income stratification; • degree of transformation of enterprises into joint-stock companies, etc.
Innovation factors	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • use of digital technologies; • information and know-how; • innovative management.

Management of the organization's personnel means ensuring the information, technical, normative-methodical, legal and business management of the personnel management system. Managers and employees of personnel management system departments also evaluate the performance of the leader and management specialist, the performance of the management system department, and the improvement of the economic efficiency of personnel management.

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